

AUTONOMY AND QUALITY OF LIFE OF INSTITUTIONALIZED ELDERLY PEOPLE WITH ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7410847

Telma Regina Stroparo

PhD student in Geography, Master in Regional Development, works as a Professor at the State University of the Midwest (Unicentro), e-mail: telma@unicentro.br

Abstract : According to data from the World Health Organization (WHO) the world population is aging and will reach the mark of 1.2 billion people over 60 years of age by 2025. Of these, a significant portion will need care in long-stay institutions, notably in due to physical or cognitive impairment. Dealing specifically with the Brazilian reality, the article aims to discuss the autonomy and quality of life of institutionalized elderly people with Alzheimer's disease. Methodologically, it is a qualitative research, with a bibliographic approach and uses a literature review to bring reflections on the problem, within the scope of public health. A literature review was carried out in article databases such as PubMed and Science Direct. The results found show the inherent difficulties in the care of patients with Alzheimer's disease, by ILPIs and multidisciplinary teams, as well as the initiatives to provide quality of life to these populations. **Keywords:** Alzheimer's. Elderly. Long-term care institution for older people . public health.

INTRODUCTION

Population aging is a worldwide phenomenon and the World Health Organization predicts that in 2025 there will be 1.2 billion people over 60 years of age, with the very elderly (aged 80 or over) constituting the age group of higher growth. (LEE PHAM, et al., 2015; STROPARO et al, 2020; STROPARO, 2021).

According to projections from the United Nations (Population Fund) “one in every 9 people in the world is aged 60 or over and it is estimated that this will increase to 1 in every 5 by 2050”. □□ In 2050, for the first time, there will be more elderly people than children under 15 years old. Data also show that the number of people aged 60 or over has increased by 178 million – equivalent to almost the total population of Pakistan, the 6th most populous country in the world (UN, 2017; BRASIL, 2015).

Elderly people are susceptible to many problems of all kinds: economic, social, mobility and especially with regard to physical health and cognitive aspects. In general, the diseases that

affect the elderly are multiple and chronic, last over the years and require constant monitoring, permanent care, continuous medication and periodic examinations (TIZOTTE et al, 2022; STROPARO, 2021; STROPARO et al, 2020; ASSOCIAÇÃO BRASILEIRA DE ALZHEIMER, 2019; LIMA, RIBEIRO, 2012).

Alois Alzheimer, German neuropathologist, discovered in 1907 the disease called Alzheimer's (AD), which is characterized by memory loss and various cognitive disorders, usually affecting individuals aged around 60 years. (SANTOS et al, 2020). According to the Ministry of Health, Alzheimer's disease (AD) is manifested by the progressive loss of memory, due to an error in the processing of certain proteins, leading to the death of neuronal tissue (MINISTÉRIO DA SAÚDE, 2020).

The World Health Organization (WHO), in a 2012 report, asserts that currently more than 35 million people worldwide have dementia, a number that is expected to double in 2030 (66 million) and triple by 2050 (115 million). Alzheimer's disease is the most common form of dementia, accounting for 60% to 70% of cases, it has no cure and there are no approved treatments that prevent the progression of symptoms. (PRINCE et al, 2014; MCKHANN, GM, et al, 2011; ALBERT et al., 2011).

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a primary neurodegenerative dementia and is a major cause of disability in the elderly (BURNS A, 2009; KNAPP et al 2014). It is a neurological, slow, degenerative disease, which leads to the progressive loss of daily domestic skills and all functions, culminating in the total loss of speech and movement, absence of thought and communication skills (SANTOS et al, 2020; MING et al, 2020; FERREIRA et al, 2014; PRINCE et al., 2014; MCKHANN, GM, et al, 2011; ALBERT et al., 2011)

According to data from the Ministry of Health, AD is manifested by the progressive loss of memory, due to an error in the processing of certain proteins, leading to the death of neuronal tissue (MINISTÉRIO DA SAÚDE, 2020). In view of the high worldwide prevalence and the social impact triggered by AD, the World Health Organization started to consider, since 2012, this disease and other related dementias among public health priorities (DUTHEY, 2013; WHO, 2012). In Brazil, a significant portion of the population affected by AD is under the care of family members. However, the incidence of said dementia is also seen in institutionalized elderly residents in so-called Long Stay Institutions for the Elderly (ILPI).

ILPI is considered to be the proposal to standardize the institutions that provide assistance to the elderly, guaranteeing conditions of physical, emotional and social well-being, in accordance, among others, with the Statute of the Elderly, with current legislation, and with public policies related to this population (STROPARO, 2021; STROPARO et al, 2020).

Most ILPIs, however, were not designed to meet the difficulties of elderly people; even so, there is a growing demand from elderly people to these institutions, both for sociocultural and financial reasons. Outsourcing care for the elderly, as a solution to serve this population, came up with improvisations that do not always meet their needs, based on social justice, legal parameters, and architectural guidelines (STROPARO, 2021; STROPARO et al, 2020; VANZIN et al, 2017). Thus, this article discusses the autonomy and quality of life of institutionalized elderly people with Alzheimer's disease.

METHODOLOGY

The research can be characterized as qualitative, with a bibliographical approach and uses a literature review to bring reflections on the problem, in the context of public health, notably spatialized in ILPI. A bibliographic review was carried out in article databases such as *PubMed* and *Science Direct* using the descriptors “institutionalized elderly”, “alzheimer's” and “quality of life”. Repeated articles published at events and those not directly related to the research theme were removed from the research portfolio.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

AD is the main cause of dementia that appears in the diagnoses of elderly people over 65 years of age, called late-onset, also reports that at least 47 million people who are diagnosed with the disease are under 60 years old of age (ALZHEIMER'S ASSOCIATION, 2020; CAZARIN; ZENAIDE, 2020). It is characterized by being a progressive disease that evolves over time and can be characterized in four stages: a) Stage 1 (initial form): changes in memory, personality and visual and spatial skills; b) Stage 2 (moderate form): difficulty speaking, performing simple tasks and coordinating movements, restlessness and insomnia; c) Stage 3 (severe form): resistance to performing daily tasks, urinary and fecal incontinence, difficulty eating, progressive motor impairment; d) Stage 4 (terminal): restriction to bed, pain on swallowing and intercurrent infections . (BOMBÓN-ALBAN; FIERRO-ALTAMIRO, 2022; MINISTRY OF HEALTH, 2011; ASSOCIAÇÃO BRASILEIRA DE ALZHEIMER, 2019; VIDOR, SAKAE and MAGAJEWSKI, 2019; BIGUETI *et al* ., 2018).

In Brazil, a significant portion of the population affected by AD is under the care of family members. However, the incidence of said dementia is also seen in institutionalized elderly residents in so-called Long Stay Institutions for the Elderly (ILPI). It is understood that ILPI is the proposal to standardize the institutions that provide assistance to the elderly, guaranteeing conditions of physical, emotional and social well-being, in accordance, among

others, with the Statute of the Elderly, with the current legislation, and with the public policies related to this population.

It is understood that institutionalization can be more humanized and work in a less rigid way, so that these places lose the stereotype of gloomy old people's deposits. Regardless of the reasons that led the elderly to refer to an institution, their citizenship rights remain intact. (STROPARO, 2021; STROPARO et al, 2020).

Most ILPIs, however, were not designed to meet the difficulties of elderly people; even so, there is a growing demand from elderly people to these institutions, both for sociocultural and financial reasons. Outsourcing care for the elderly, as a solution to meet this demand, came up with improvisations that do not always meet their needs, based on social justice, legal parameters, and architectural guidelines (VANZIN et al, 2017). It discusses the growing need for civil organization to house part of this population in institutions that promote the necessary basic care, with physical and cognitive autonomy as well as quality of life for those assisted.

Dealing specifically with quality of life, there is the group of scholars from the World Health Organization (WHO), *The WHOQOL Group*, which proposes a concept for subjective, multidimensional quality of life that includes positive and negative elements: “quality of life It is an individual's perception of their position in life, in the context of the culture and value systems in which they live, and in relation to their goals, expectations, standards and concerns”. (WHOQOL, 1995, p. 1405). It is a broad and complex concept that encompasses physical health, psychological state, level of independence, social relationships, personal beliefs and relationship with the characteristics of the environment. Furthermore, there are already validated instruments adapted to the Brazilian cultural context that can be used to measure the quality of life in institutionalized environments. (BOMBÓN-ALBAN; FIERRO-ALTAMIRO, 2022; FLECK, 2008; FLECK, 2000;)

The fundamental principles of aging with QoL describe the elderly as proactive, defining their goals and fighting to achieve them, gathering resources that are useful in adapting to change and actively involved in maintaining well-being in a changing and not always favorable world (BOMBÓN-ALBAN; FIERRO-ALTAMIRO, 2022).

It is understood that the State and society need public policies and civil organization to welcome these elderly people with dignity, especially in vulnerable conditions in such a way that they have access to public services. Those who are unable for cognitive and/or physical reasons who, likewise, have access to multidisciplinary health services that guarantee them dignity, comfort and quality of life. The incentive to autonomy must be urgent and, as long as it is safe and possible, allowed.

CONCLUSION

With the phenomenon of world population aging, there is an accentuated need to discuss the subject in the spheres of public policies and in civil society that need to organize themselves to meet the demand and welcome this population with quality of life.

In Brazil, the so-called ILPI stands out, which aim to provide shelter for these elderly people, especially those who are in vulnerable conditions due to the lack of family members, physical and cognitive impairments, poverty, etc.

The problems are accentuated with dementia and, in particular, AD, which causes progressive disability in the elderly. Providing adequate living conditions, with multidisciplinary and dignified care, has been a challenge for ILPI, which are normally financially deficient.

REFERENCES

ALBERT, MARILYN S. et al. The diagnosis of mild cognitive impairment due to Alzheimer's disease: recommendations from the National Institute on Aging-Alzheimer's Association workgroups on diagnostic guidelines for Alzheimer's disease. **Alzheimer's & dementia** , v. 7, no. 3, p. 270-279, 2011. DOI 10.1016/j.jalz.2011.03.008

ALZHEIMER'S ASSOCIATION. Alz.org/Brazil. **Information about Alzheimer's and dementia. Alzheimer's and dementia. Inside the Brain: An Interactive Journey** . 2020. Available at: <https://www.alz.org/br/passeio-pelo-c%C3%A9rebro-interativo.aspr>.

ABRAZ, Brazilian Alzheimer's Association. **Insanity. What are the signs of Alzheimer's Disease?**. 2019 . Available at: <https://abraz.org.br/2020/sobre-alzheimer/demencia-2/>.

BIGUETI, BCP *et al* . Essential nutrients in the prevention of Alzheimer's disease. **Nutritional Sciences Online** , Bebedouro, v. 2, no. 2, p. 18-25, Mar. 2018

BOMBÓN-ALBÁN, PE; FIERRO-ALTAMIRANO, PE Diagnostic criteria for Alzheimer's disease: Practical applications. **Revista Ecuatoriana de Neurología** , v. 31, no. 1, 2022.

BRAZIL, Ministry of Health. Health from A to Z. **Alzheimer's: what it is, causes, symptoms, treatment, diagnosis and prevention**. 2022. Available at: <https://saude.gov.br/saude-de-az/alzheimer>

FLECK, MPA Conceptual problems in quality of life. In: FLECK, Marcelo Pio de Almeida et al. (Org.). **Assessing quality of life** : a guide for health professionals. Porto Alegre: Artmed, 2008. p.19-28.

FLECK, MPA The World Health Organization's quality of life assessment instrument (WHOQOL-100): characteristics and perspectives. **Ciência & Saúde Coletiva** , 5(1):3338, 2000.

FERREIRA, LL et al. Functional capacity of institutionalized elderly with and without Alzheimer's disease. **Brazilian Journal of Geriatrics and Gerontology** , v. 17, p. 567-573, 2014. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1809-9823.2014.13102>

UNITED NATIONS POPULATION FUND. Aging in the 21st Century: Celebration and Challenge. Executive Summary. New York; 2012. Available at https://www.unfpa.org/sites/default/files/pub-pdf/Portuguese-Exec-Summary_0.pdf

KNAPP M, COMAS-HERRERA A, WITTENBERG R, HU B, KING D, REHILL A, ADELAJA B. Scenarios of dementia care: What are the impacts on cost and quality of life? PSSRU Discussion Paper, 2878, **Personal Social Services Research Unit** , London, UK. 2014.

LAWTON, MP Quality of life in Alzheimer disease. **Alzheimer disease and associated disorders** , v. 8, p. 138-150, 1994.

LEE PHAM, PD; VO, Trung Quang. Assessment of psychometric properties of WHOQOL-OLD instrument: a literature review. **International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Research** , Baltimore, v. 4, no. 4, p. 53-66, 2015.

LIMA, D.; LIMA, M.; RIBEIRO, C. Aging and quality of life of institutionalized elderly. **Brazilian Journal of Human Aging Sciences** , v. 7, no. 3, 22 Apr. 2012. <https://doi.org/10.5335/rbceh.2012.782>

MCKHANN, GM, et al. The diagnosis of dementia due to Alzheimer's disease: recommendations from the National Institute on Aging-Alzheimer's Association workgroups on diagnostic guidelines for Alzheimer's disease. **Alzheimer's & dementia : the journal of the Alzheimer's Association**, 7 (3), 263–269. 2011. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jalz.2011.03.005>

MING, Y. et al. Association of oral health–related quality of life and Alzheimer disease: a systematic review. **The Journal of prosthetic dentistry** , v. 124, no. 2, p. 168-175, 2020.

UNITED NATIONS ORGANIZATION. UN Summit discusses population aging and sustainable development. 2017. Available at: <https://nacoesunidas.org/cupula-da-onu-discute-envelhecimento-populacional-edesenvolvimento-sustentavel/>

PRINCE M, ALBANESE E, GUERCHET M, PRINA M. World Alzheimer Report **Dementia and Risk Reduction** : Analysis of protective and modifiable factors. Alzheimer's Disease International (ADI), London, 2014;104p.

SANTOS, CF et al. Alzheimer's disease: a bibliographical review. **Revista Higei@-Revista Científica de Saúde** , v. 2, no. 4, 2020

SOUZA COSTA, MCN; MERCADANTE, EF **Elderly living in an ILPI (Long Stay Institution for the Elderly) and what this represents for the elderly subject** . *Kairós Magazine: Gerontology*, v. 16, no. 1, p. 209-222, 2013.

STROPARO, TR Smart Cities, Urban Mobility and Human Aging in Times of Pandemic: Exclusion and Isolation. **Conjuncture Bulletin (BOCA)** , v. 5, no. 14, p. 102-109, 2021.

STROPARO, T.R; EIDAM, Fabiele; CZAIKOVSKI, Maria L. Costs in long-term care facilities for the elderly (ILPI): meanings and repercussions on the quality of life of institutionalized elderly people. **Brazilian Journal of Development** , vol. 6, no. 7, p. 47956-47970, 2020.

SIEWERT JS, ALVAREZ A. M, SANTOS SMA D, BRITO F. A, HAMMERSCHMIDT KSA Institutionalized elderly people with dementia: an integrative review on nursing care. *Rev Bras Enferm.* 2020;73 Suppl 3:e20180419. <https://doi.org/10.1590/0034-7167-2018-0419>

BRAZILIAN SOCIETY OF GERIATRICS AND GERONTOLOGY. With population aging, Alzheimer's disease is expected to increase in the coming decades, points out SBGG. 2018. Available at: <https://sbgg.org.br/com-o-envelhecimento-populacional-doenca-de-alzheimer-devera-aumentar-nas-proximas-decadas-aponta-sbgg/>

TIZOTTE, T.; MUELLER, A.; THESING, N.; GALLI, N.; MONTENEGRO, J. . Evolution of the dependency ratio and population aging rate within the scope of the 28 COREDEs in Rio Grande do Sul. **Conjectures** , [S. l.] , v. 22, no. 6, p. 59–73, 2022. DOI: 10.53660/CONJ-1032-002

VANZIN, T; PEREIRA, M.B; GONÇALVES, BP Systematic observations in Long Stay Institutions for the Elderly (ILPI): Architectural considerations. **Kairós Magazine: Gerontology** , v. 20, no. 4, p. 195-208, 2017

VIDOR, R.C; SAKAE, T.M; MAGAJEWSKI, FRL Mortality from Alzheimer's disease and human development in the 21st century: an ecological study in major Brazilian regions. **ACM arch. catarin. med.**, Florianópolis, v. 48, no. 1, p. 94-107, Mar. 2019

WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION (WHO). **Dementia** : a public health priority. Geneva: WHO, 2012.

WHOQOL. WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION QUALITY OF LIFE GROUP. The World Health Organization Quality of Life assessment (WHOQOL): position paper from the World Health Organization. **Social Science and Medicine** , vol. 41, no. 10, p. 1403-1409, 1995.